

Table 2. Correlation coefficients of relationships among parameters of crop performance, soil properties, crop and pest management, and pest intensity measured in farmers' fields at rainfed lowland sites in Vietnam and northeast Thailand. Data are pooled across plots that received different intensities of pest control.^a 1992.

	YIELD	NAPP	NOWEED ^b	NOPEST	VDIS	VDISINS	GDISINS	VGDISINS	WCOVER
CLAY	.35	.59**	.12	.47*	.72**	.73**	.57**	.69**	.27
SILT	.51**	.65**	.25	.64**	.67**	.72**	.68**	.66**	.35
SAND	-.45*	-.67**	-.19	-.59**	-.77**	-.79**	-.66**	-.74**	-.33
TLAYER	.58**	.59**	.13	.57**	.70**	.71**	.44*	.58**	.22
CARBON	.75**	.60**	.29	.61**	.72**	.75**	.61**	.71**	.35
PH	-.37**	.15	-.24*	-.04	-.10	-.14	.08	.03	-.01
CEC	.48**	.41**	.10	.17	.62**	.63**	.52**	.64**	.20
P	.56**	.40**	.39**	.28*	.49**	.54**	.18	.34**	.23
K	-.00	.02	-.14	-.08	-.18	-.17	-.09	-.01	-.02
NAPP	.45*	.	.32	.74**	.61**	.68**	.63**	.66**	.56**
NOWEED	.32	.32	.	.44*	.36	.41*	.29	.36	.49*
NOPEST	.63**	.74**	.44*	.	.62**	.66**	.51**	.56**	.48*
AYIELD	.67**	.76**	.33	.81**	.77**	.81**	.67**	.76**	.56**
VDIS	.51**	.61**	.36	.62**	.	.98**	.59**	.82**	.42*
VDISINS	.53**	.68**	.41*	.66**	.98**	.	.60**	.83**	.52**
GDISINS	.31	.63**	.29	.51**	.59**	.60**	.	.90**	.27
VGDISINS	.40*	.66**	.36	.56**	.82**	.83**	.90**	.	.39*
WCOVER	.30	.56**	.49*	.48*	.42*	.52**	.27	.39*	.

^aVDIS = % total disease on vegetative plant parts; VDISINS = % total disease and insect damage on vegetative plant parts; GDISINS = % total disease and insect damage on generative plant parts and on whole tillers; VGDISINS = VDISINS + GDISINS; for definition of other parameters, see Table 1; one-tailed test, n = 93; * = significant at p = 0.01; ** = significant at p = 0.001; correlation coefficients were truncated; pest control treatments: a) no control, b) control according to farmers' practices, c) pest control 4-5 times during growing season. ^bNOWEED = number of weed control measures (hand weeding and/or herbicide application).

vegetative phase at some sites in Vietnam.

A wide spectrum of disease and insect damage was observed. Severity ratings of biotic constraints were generally higher at sites in Vietnam than at those in Thailand. High severity ratings of dirty panicles and weed infestation were observed in both countries. Noticeable levels of leaf scald, brown spot, red stripe, root rot, sheath blight, leaf folder damage, whitehead damage, and discoloration due to sucking insects (especially on panicles), tiller damage caused by rats and other pests, and seedbed damage due

to thrips and/or mole crickets were observed, mainly in Vietnam.

Correlation analyses showed a complex structure of intercorrelations among parameters of crop performance, soil fertility and water-holding capacity, crop and pest management intensity, and pest intensity (Table 2). High actual yields of sites, high physiological potential production levels as determined by parameters of soil fertility and water-holding capacity, high fertilizer and pest control inputs, and high pest intensities were closely associated.

Pest intensity may primarily depend

on the physiological potential production level and not on the intensity of pest control while the willingness of farmers to invest in pest control may mainly depend on a site's yield potential. In this light, cause-effect relationships between site-specific conditions and pest problems and the profitability of pest control need to be critically examined. The data can be useful for characterizing patterns of and interrelations among cropping and pest control practices, factors determining productivity level, and pest problems in rainfed lowland rice areas. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Efficacy of three fungicides for controlling growth of five seedborne fungi associated with rice grain spotting

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Many fungi may cause rice grain spotting. The presence of fungi and discoloration reduce rice seed quality. Fungi may appear externally on the lemma and palea and/or internally in the grain. Grains with black dots, pigmentation, chalkiness, and stains from the Province of Corrientes, Argentina, were studied. We isolated 10 fungi from field-infected panicles using the blotter test method, following the rules of the International

Seed Testing Association. The following were selected for an in vitro control test due to their importance and frequency: *Bipolaris oryzae*, *Curvularia lunata*, an unidentified species, and *Fusarium semitectum*. *Fusarium moniliforme* was included as an ordinary pathogenic control species.

We used fungicides thiabendazole, carbendazim, and mancozeb. Solutions were prepared using 50, 100, 500, and

Effect of chemical treatments on some fungi that cause rice grain spotting.^a

Treatment	Concentration (ppm)	Fungus species growth ^b (ϕ cm)									
		<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	<i>Curvularia lunata</i>	Unidentified	<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i>	<i>Fusarium semitectum</i>					
Thiabendazole	0	2.74	de	3.80	d	2.01	c	4.83	c	4.85	a
	50	2.95	cd	3.20	e	0.60	g	0.60	g	0.60	f
	100	2.92	cde	2.53	e	0.60	g	0.60	g	0.60	f
	500	3.12	bcd	2.07	h	0.60	g	0.60	g	0.60	f
	1000	2.84	cde	2.14	gh	0.60	g	0.60	g	0.60	f
Carbendazim	0	2.91	cde	5.77	ab	3.71	a	5.78	a	4.50	b
	50	3.57	a	5.89	a	0.97	ef	0.60	g	0.60	f
	100	3.60	a	5.72	b	0.73	fg	0.60	g	0.60	f
	500	3.50	ab	5.78	ab	0.60	g	0.60	g	0.60	f
	1000	3.20	abc	5.85	ab	0.60	g	0.60	g	0.60	f
Mancozeb	0	2.49	e	4.69	c	2.85	b	5.65	b	4.49	b
	50	3.15	bcd	2.24	g	2.64	b	4.88	c	4.20	c
	100	2.78	cde	2.15	gh	2.81	b	4.68	d	4.52	b
	500	1.59	f	1.33	i	1.47	d	4.42	e	3.60	d
	1000	1.00	g	0.60	j	1.24	de	3.95	f	3.42	e

^aMean of 4 replications. ^bIn a column, means followed by common letters are not significantly different at 5% by DMRT.

1,000 ppm sterile distilled water. For each, 1 ml of the fungicide solution was mixed with glucose potato agar (GPA), melted at 50 °C, and poured in petri dishes. Agar slugs (6-mm-diam disks) of each species were then centered in the dishes containing the agar and fungicide concentrations.

Each concentration was replicated four times as was the control sample (0 ppm) in which 1 ml distilled water was added to the melted agar. Petri dishes were kept in an incubator at 25 °C. We measured colony diameters on days 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10.

A totally random design was used and a factor analysis of data was performed. Duncan's multiple range test was applied to evaluate the differences between mean values.

Of the three products, mancozeb had the greatest efficacy on *B. oryzae* and *C. lunata*, with the greatest effect at 500 ppm. Carbendazim and thiabendazole had good efficacy at 50 ppm in controlling the growth of *F. semitectum*, *F. moniliforme*, and the unidentified species. ■

Leafhopper transmission of the Philippine isolate of rice dwarf virus

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Rice dwarf virus (RDV) is a new viral disease of rice in the Philippines. It is presently found only in Midsayap, North Cotabato. Several leafhopper species are known vectors of the disease in countries where it occurs. We determined which leafhopper species transmit RDV in the Philippines.

Second-instar nymphs of *Nephotettix nigropictus*, *N. virescens*, and *Recilia*

dorsalis were allowed 4 d of access to RDV-infected Taichung Native 1 (TN1) plants. They were transferred to healthy TN1 seedlings for 4 d, and then, individually used to inoculate a 6-d-old TN1

Transmission of rice dwarf virus (RDV) by 3 species of leafhoppers.

Species	Insects tested (no.)	Insects that transmitted (no.)	Incubation period in vector (d)
<i>N. nigropictus</i>	400	40	8-23
<i>N. virescens</i>	400	0	-
<i>R. dorsalis</i>	400	0	-
Transovarial passage ^a			
<i>N. nigropictus</i>	579	60	0-2

^aInsects hatching from eggs of all female adults with access to RDV-infected plants.

seedling in a test tube. Until they died, insects were transferred daily to fresh seedlings. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted in pots and scored 1 mo after inoculation.

To test for transovarial passage of the virus, 2d- to 3d-instar nymphs of *N. nigropictus* were given access to a diseased plant for 4 d and then reared on healthy TN1 seedlings until they became adults. All female adults were selected and confined on healthy TN1 seedlings to lay eggs for 3 d. Nymphs that hatched were immediately tested for RDV transmission as above.

Among the three leafhopper species tested, only *N. nigropictus* transmitted RDV (see table). About 10% of those tested were active transmitters. The virus is persistent in the vector and has an incubation period of 8-23 d (av of 15 d). RDV was also passed through transovarial passage to the progenies of viruliferous insects. About 10% of the insects were congenitally infective. Eight percent of them transmitted RDV immediately after hatching.

RDV had an incubation period of about 9 d in the rice plant. The first sign of RDV infection was minute white specks on emerging leaves. Leaf symptoms became more conspicuous 3-4 wk after inoculation. Stunting on TN1 was very mild. Infected plants looked normal except for the white specks or streaks on leaf blades. Plants grown from seeds of infected plants did not show RDV symptoms.

Our results showed that *N. nigropictus* is the main vector of RDV in the Philippines and was not transmitted, as in other countries, by *N. virescens* and *R. dorsalis*. This difference in vector transmission may be due to either a difference in the colony of insects used or a difference in RDV strain. ■